

Synthesis of some New Derivatives from *N*¹-Acetylhydrazido-quinolin-2(1*H*)-ones

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Quinoline derivatives possess a variety of biological activities¹. In the present investigation, we report the synthesis of *N*¹-substituted quinoline derivatives. Since, hydrazides, thiosemicarbazides, triazoles, oxadiazoles and thiadiazoles are associated with antibacterial activity, it was considered worthwhile to incorporate these structural moieties in the *N*¹-position of quinoline nucleus.

The strategy employed in the synthesis of desired compound involved carbethoxymethylation of 4-methyl quinoline-2(1*H*)-ones (1) to form *N*¹-carbethoxymethylquinoline-2(1*H*)-ones (2) which when reacted with hydrazine hydrate in ethanol gave *N*¹-acetylhydrazido-4-methylquinoline-2(1*H*)-ones (3). The reaction of 3 with phenyl isocyanate yielded quinoline-2(1*H*)-onylmethylthiosemicarbazides (4) as key intermediates. 4a when cyclised in presence of sodium hydroxide, I₂ in KI and phosphoric acid furnished targeted 1-phenyl-5-mercapto-2-(4'-methylquinolin-2'-onemeth-1'-yl)-1, 3, 4-triazole (5a), anilino-2-(4'-methylquinolin-2'-onemeth-1'-yl)-1, 3, 4-oxadiazole (6a) and 5-anilino-2-(4'-methylquinoline-2'-onemeth-1'-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (7a) respectively. The structures of the compounds were confirmed by ir, pmr and elemental analysis data.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 237 spectrophotometer and pmr spectra (TFA) on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. Purity

of the compounds was checked by tlc using silica gel G.

Substituted quinolin-2-ones (**1**) were prepared by known method⁹.

N¹-Carbathoxymethyl-4-methyl quinolin-2(1H)-ones (2a-c): A mixture of 4-methylquinolin-2(1H)-one (**1a**; 0.03 mol) and methylchloroacetate (0.03 mol) in dry acetone containing anhydrous potassium carbonate (2 g) was refluxed for 24 h, then cooled and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting white solid was washed with water and recrystallised from ethanol: **4a** (86%), m.p. 68° (Found: C, 67.40; H, 5.60; N, 6.00. C₁₃H₁₃ON requires: C, 67.53; H, 5.63; N, 6.06%); ν_{\max} 1 780 (ester C=O), 1 665 (amido C=O) and 1 600 cm⁻¹ (C=C); δ 2.45 (3H, s, =C-CH₃), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.95 (2H, s, NCH₂), 6.15 (1H, s, =CH-) and 7.0-7.6 (4H, m, ArH); **4b** (86%), 165°; **4c** (88%) 243°.

N¹-Acetylhydrazido-4-methylquinolin-2(1H)-ones (3a-c): To a solution of **2a** (0.01 mol) in ethanol (40 ml), hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h, then cooled and the resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol: **3a** (82%), m.p. 284° (Found: C, 62.45; H, 5.58; N, 18.00. C₁₂H₁₂O₂N₂ requires: C, 62.54; H, 5.63; N, 18.18%); ν_{\max} 3 350 (NHNH₂), 1 665 (amido C=O); δ 2.4 (3H, s, =C-CH₃), 2.5 (2H, s, NH₂), 3.92 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 6.2 (1H, s, =CH-) 7.0-7.5 (4H, m, ArH) and 8.2 (1H, s br, CONH exchangeable with D₂O); **3b** (92%), 298°; **3c** (78%), 317°.

4-Phenyl-1-(N¹-quinolinomethyl)thiosemicarbazides (4a-c): A mixture of **3a** (0.001 mol) and phenyl isothiocyanate (0.001 mol) in ethanol (25 ml) was refluxed for 3-4 h, then cooled and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The resulting residue was triturated with water and the solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol: **4a** (63%), m.p. 187° (Found: C, 62.00; H, 4.85; N, 15.10. C₁₉H₁₈O₂N₄S requires: C, 62.30; H, 4.92; N, 15.30%); ν_{\max} 3 350-3 400 (NH), 1 670 br (CONH) and 1 325-1 355 (C=S); δ 2.4 (3H, s, =C-CH₃), 3.90 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 6.18 (1H, s, =CH), 7.2-7.6 (9H, m, ArH) and 7.8 (1H, s, NHCO exchangeable with D₂O); **4b** (65%) 105°; **4c** (80%), 73°.

5-Phenyl-2-[N¹-(4'-methyl quinolin-2'-onemethyl-yl)]-5-mercapto-1,3,4-triazole (5a): Compound **4a** (0.001 mol) was refluxed with 2N NaOH (2 ml) for 3 h, then cooled and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with glacial acetic acid to give a solid

which when recrystallised from ethanol, (62%), m.p. 296° (Found: C, 65.50; H, 4.55; N, 16.00. C₁₉H₁₆N₄OS requires: C, 65.52; H, 4.60; N, 16.09%); ν_{\max} 3 250-3 300 (NH), 1 665 (amido cyclic C=O) and 1 620 (C=N); δ 2.4 (3H, s, =C-CH₃), 3.95 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 6.15 (1H, s, =CH), 7.0-7.9 (9H, m, ArH) and 11.5-12.0 (1H, s, exchangeable with D₂O, SH).

5-Anilino-2-(4'-methylquinolin-2'-onemethyl-yl)-1,3,4-oxadiazole (6a): To a mixture of **4a** (0.001 mol) in NaOH (4N; 4 ml), I₂ in KI was added till the colour of I₂ persisted and the reaction mixture was further concentrated for 4-5 h, then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol, (66%), m.p. 278 (Found: C, 68.68; H, 4.75; N, 16.80. C₁₂H₁₀O₂N₄ requires: C, 68.67; H, 4.82; N, 16.85%); ν_{\max} 3 150-3 250 (NH), 1 665-1 670 (NHCO) and 1 620 (C=N); δ 2.45 (3H, s, =C-CH₃), 4.00 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.5 (1H, s, NH), 6.12 (1H, s, =CH) and 7.0-7.5 (9H, m, ArH).

5-Anilino-2-(4'-methyl quinazolin-2-onemethyl-yl)-1,3,4-thiadiazole (7a): Compound **4a** (0.001 mol) dissolved in phosphoric acid (5 ml) was heated at 120° for 50 min, then kept overnight and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol, (73%), m.p. 55° (Found: C, 68.60; H, 4.75; N, 16.80. C₁₉H₁₆ON₄S requires: C, 68.67; H, 4.82; N, 16.85%); ν_{\max} 3 200-3 300 (NH), 1 665 (amido C=O), 1 610-1 620 (C=N) and 700-720 (C-S-C); δ 2.4 (3H, s, =C-CH₃), 4.0 (2H, s, N-CH₂), 4.8 (1H, s, NH), 6.15 (1H, s, =CH) and 7.0-7.8 (9H, m, ArH).

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